

»LLMs for everything?« Potentials and Problems of the Application of In-Context Learning for Computational Literature Studies¹

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Large Language Models (LLMs) have revolutionized Natural Language Processing (NLP) since the advent of the transformer-architecture in the last few years. At least since the publication of ChatGPT, the potential of these models has also become widely known to the non-academic public. One feature of these models that has not yet been fully explained is that as their number of parameters grows – around 10 billion parameters is mentioned here as a threshold value – they also develop problem-solving abilities for which they have not been trained (Wei et al. 2022). These so-called »emergent abilities« also include a training method that is not strictly speaking a »classical« form of fine-tuning, since no adjustments are made to the weights: in-context learning (ICL, Dong et al. 2023).

ICL refers to any task that an LLM performs by only being conditioned through a prompt text. Such prompts consist either of explicit instructions or examples written in natural language to convey the »knowledge« contained and implied in those examples or a combination of both.

As Brown et al. (2020) have already shown, GPT-3 can solve a variety of complex tasks with the help of ICL. The reasons why they do so have not yet been elucidated in detail. Recent studies suggest that the fact that the examples used are plausible or true for the task is less important than other factors such as the underlying distribution of the examples or their format (Min et al. 2022). Clavie et al. (2023) show, for example, that in the binary classification of qualification requirements for a job advertisement, large LLMs such as OpenAI's *text-davinci-003* model clearly outperform classical ML-approaches such as SVM, but also smaller »foundational models« such as DeBERTaV3. Ziems et al. (2023), who investigated the potential of ICL for the Computational Social Sciences, came to a similar conclusion. They also achieved the best results with selected classification tasks whose annotation schemes – according to their hypothesis – corresponded to the implicit definitions of everyday language concepts.

For Digital Humanities in general, and for Computational Literary Studies (CLS) in particular, ICL is attractive at first glance because, first, it works with natural-language prompts and thus requires neither deep programming skills nor detailed knowledge of the modeling practices of LLMs. Second, the fact that it works with natural language input suggests that ICL can import the traditional conceptual and definitional practices of the humanities into NLP without much operationalization effort, which still represent a major challenge for complex concepts in the humanities (Pichler/Reiter 2022). Third, ICL does not require the time-consuming task of (manually) generating training data.

In what follows, we will explore the potential of ICL using a specific example from the CLS. This is an attempt to replicate or surpass the results of the operationalization and modeling of statements defined as “generalizing” from Andrew Piper’s *Can We Be Wrong?* (2020). The aim of Piper's operationalization and modeling is to investigate »text-empirically« what role generalizations play in literary studies. To answer this question, he develops a workflow that

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roughly corresponds to the workflow that we developed at the same time in CRETA and that we call ›reflective text analysis‹ (Reiter/Pichler 2020): Based on aforementioned question, Piper and his team developed an operationalization of the concept of ›generalizing statements‹ and its subconcepts, created an annotation scheme, iteratively improved it, and finally trained different ML models on the annotated data (Piper 2020, 17-21).

As part of the operationalization process, Piper and his team arrived at a definition of generalization that understands the concept as a linguistic phenomenon that must be validated externalistically: »[G]eneralization is something that is at once linguistically legible at the statement level – it has certain criteria or qualities – and is also ambiguous. [...] It depends on real-world knowledge of the generality of the terms being used with respect to some context and the definitional certainty that links subject and predicate.« (Piper 2020, 27). According to Piper, the annotation and modeling process was as follows (Piper 2020, 32-34): In an initial annotation run, 116 sentences from articles not included in the eventual training dataset were annotated by Piper and three other members of the team, and then measured to see how Piper’s annotations matched the majority vote of the other three annotators. Piper then annotated an additional 3500 sentences based on the annotation guidelines. These annotations were then used to train several machine learning models. The manually annotated categories *generalization* and *exemplification* were combined into a single category, since only a few instances of the latter were found during manual annotation. Ultimately, this was a binary classification task. In the following, we will focus on the results of these models and, for reasons of space, neglect the equally relevant discussion of the consequences that Piper drew from the application of these models.

The models trained by Piper and his team on the approximately balanced data achieved F1 scores between 0.591 and 0.769 and accuracy values between 0.638 and 0.745, with the best performing model being a CNN with ELMo embeddings, where recall significantly exceeds precision (Piper 2020, 34). For our experiments, we worked with OpenAI's proprietary *text-davinci-003 model*,² which was at the time recommended by OpenAI for these purposes, and developed 11 different ICL templates for it after a short exploration phase.³ These included both so-called zero-shot prompts – input of the task description without examples – and different types of few-shot prompts – input that includes examples with or without further contextual information. Our results with these templates are in the middle of the results of Piper and his team, with the highest F1 score of 0.69 and an accuracy of 0.69 for a template containing four examples with the instruction »Determine the class of the incoming sentence as ›generalization‹ or ›neutral‹ on the base of the following examples.«

	Modell	F1-Score	Accuracy
Piper (2020)	cnn + ELMo	0.769	0.745
	bilstm + ELMo	0.757	0.741
	stacked bilstm + ELMo	0.750	0.729

² The total cost amounted to around 260 US dollars.

³ The data, the Python script and a jupyter notebook for your own exploration can be found at: <https://github.com/nilsreiter/dhd2024-few-shot>

	Modell	F1-Score	Accuracy
	lstm + ELMo	0.742	0.724
	bert	0.736	0.703
	cnn (GloVe)	0.696	0.696
	stacked bilstm (GloVe)	0.665	0.669
	lstm (GloVe)	0.595	0.641
	bilstm (GloVe)	0.591	0.638
Diese Arbeit	Input: the sentence to be classified + instruction to assign it to one of the two categories (zero_shot)	0.620	0.644
	Input: Like zero_shot, but with the addition »think step-by-step« (zero_shot_reason)	0.621	0.644
	Input of four examples and their classification + sentence to be classified (few_shot)	0.574	0.481
	Input: Structure like few_shot, but including the explanation of the task (few_shot_inst)	0.678	0.678
	Input: Structure like few_shot_inst, but including the explanation of the role of the model (few_shot_inst_role)	0.684	0.686
	Input: Structure like few_shot_inst_role, but including a description of the two classes (few_shot_inst_role_exp)	0.659	0.659
	Input: Structure like few_shot, but other examples (few_shot_2)	0.649	0.596
	Input: Structure like few_shot_inst, but other examples (few_shot_inst_2)	0.691	0.696
	Input: Structure like few_shot_inst_role, but other examples (few_shot_inst_role_2)	0.669	0.683
	Input: Structure like few_shot_inst_role_exp, but other examples (few_shot_inst_role_exp_2)	0.598	0.642

Table 1: Classification results in Piper (2020) and experiments with an LLM

The best ICL method thus achieves a performance that is 5-7 percentage points lower than the best model described by Piper. Contrary to examples from other areas, the performance here is not significantly better than when working with smaller ›foundational models‹ such as BERT. In this specific case, we consider the following possibilities as plausible causes for this: First, the explanation of the distinction between ›generalization‹ and ›neutral‹ is not common in everyday language – although one speaks of generalizing statements, one does not generally refer to all statements that do not fall into this class as ›neutral‹. Piper’s theoretically based

classification scheme is therefore not supported by common language usage.⁴ If one follows Min et al. in their – thoroughly speculative – hypothesis that ICL works all the better the more it can build on categorical differentiations already present in the training data of the LLM, their possible absence in the latter could explain the relatively low scores. Second, there is some leeway in the choice of examples. In the experiments, we concentrated on those examples that Piper himself used in the text of his monograph and that we therefore considered to be exemplary. However, we did not use any known sampling techniques to select the examples, nor did we manually check the representativeness of the data annotated in detail by Piper and his team. What, if any, performance gains are possible in this way would need to be clarified. In addition to these specific questions about the relatively weak performance of ICL with respect to Piper’s data, we would like to point out other potential problem areas and open questions regarding the use of in-context learning in CLS. These include the fundamental danger that ICL’s focus on examples invites the undefined and unreflected use of concepts. If, as in our case, the best results are achieved with a prompt that does not include a definition of the concepts used, this invites the user to refrain from defining these terms in the first place. The problematic consequences of such an approach are obvious: without having defined the concepts, re-importing the results into subject-specific discourse runs the risk of obscuring their scope, since the mere mention of examples allows for different interpretations of the extension of these concepts. This means that the validity of the concept in the specific domain is at risk. Second, a similar danger exists even if the term is defined before and for the ICL, because the mechanisms behind it have not yet been clarified. With a prompt consisting of a definition, an instruction, and an example, the user does not know which of the three components is ultimately decisive for the classification. Whether it is actually the definition that is used remains unclear. Third, this leads to another fundamental problem with using commercial LLMs: commercial providers like OpenAI do not make their models publicly available. This adds to the already widely discussed opacity of LLMs per se. Fourth, LLMs like the OpenAI *text-davinci-003* model used here are not deterministic. Accordingly, the results are not stable, even if one uses hyperparameters to ensure this, such as a temperature of 0.

In CLS, the obligation to define one’s central concepts in the course of the operationalization or annotation process (which categories are assigned when, what they mean, where annotations begin and end, etc.) is often cited as an advantage of computational methods over more ›traditional‹ literary studies (e.g. Meister 1995), since the latter’s terms are »usually too vague or too abstract to be clearly formalized« (Meister 2012, 294). Although the view that literary studies’ concepts should be made more precise on the basis of standard language usage in order to eliminate vagueness and ambiguity from literary studies (Fricke 1989), which has been propagated by Harald Fricke for several decades, now forms the theoretical basis of the German *Reallexikon der deutschsprachigen Literaturwissenschaft*, it still does not seem to dominate the practice of the discipline, as Meister’s quote suggests. With the use of LLMs, this obligation even no longer applies in CLS, and the terminology runs the risk of becoming correspondingly imprecise and blurred.

⁴ This is the first example of a neutral sentence in the annotated data from Piper and his team: »To this end, one of the main merits of Merleau-Ponty’s framing of cinema as art is that it is not wedded to celluloid film and the oft-discussed reality effect its highly indexical-iconic images.« The annotated sentences can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12669329.v1>

In our view, this means the following for the use of ICL in CLS: First, regardless of the language model used for text analysis, the concepts central to the analysis should be defined and, ideally, a reference dataset should be manually created. In this way, even opaque models can be empirically grounded in a way that facilitates the confirmation and validity of the analyses, or in some cases makes them possible at all. Second, if you decide to use ICL, you should first work with smaller samples to check whether ICL actually outperforms traditional methods: for concepts whose definitions differ from everyday usage, fine-tuning a pre-trained language model (PLM) such as BERT may be more effective. Third, the question-specific performance of commercial LLMs from the big tech companies should be compared with that of open-source models. This not only saves money and resources, but also makes sense in terms of scientific ethics, since models such as Stanford's Alpaca or Vicuna currently release both their source code and their training data with a performance close to that of commercial vendors.

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